

Research

Research on Investment Strategies Considering Investors' Emotions Based on Optimized CNN Algorithm

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Abstract: This paper explores how to extract investor sentiment in text using an optimized convolutional neural network algorithm and form investor opinions based on it, so as to construct a portfolio model with a higher rate of return. Specifically, based on the text data of SSE 50 constituent stocks in the Oriental Fortune stock bar, the optimized convolutional neural network algorithm is used to classify the sentiment, and then calculate the daily investor sentiment indicator; further, the sentiment indicator, the stock closing price, and the trading volume are used as the inputs of the long- and short-term memory network to predict the future returns of the stocks; finally, the prediction results are used as the investor's viewpoints to construct the portfolio model with a higher return. Finally, the prediction results are placed in the Black-Litterman model to construct a portfolio model that takes investor sentiment into account. The backtest results show that the optimized convolutional neural network algorithm-based portfolio model with investor sentiment has better performance.

Keywords: investor sentiment, portfolio, convolutional neural network algorithm, long and short-term memory networks, sentiment classification,

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1 Introduction

Behavioral finance believes that stock prices are not only affected by stock historical data, but also by investor sentiment. Early investor sentiment research was conducted through questionnaires and other forms^[1], with the rapid development of the Internet, the network has become the main source of information and dissemination media, investors can instantly access and express bullish or bearish views on the relevant stocks through the Internet, thereby identifying positive or negative news, so as to make the corresponding investment behavior or decision-making. For example, Wen Fenghua^[2] used SSE market data to construct investor sentiment and studied the behavioral characteristics of investors under different emotions. Zhang Xindong and Yuan Dongliang^[3] based on "bull market" and "bear market" and other words in the microblogging daily number of times to construct the investor sentiment factor that can improve

the timeliness. Lu Xiaopeng^[4] quantifies investor sentiment by using the daily posting volume of Ideal Forum, and the results show that the fluctuation of this sentiment indicator coincides with the rise and fall of the broader market index. Nguyen^[5] extracts investment sentiments from social media to predict stock prices, and achieves better results in empirical tests. Duan Jiangjiao^[6] found that investor sentiment and sentiment consistency have a significant effect on daily return, daily trading volume and daily volatility of individual stocks.

As natural language processing technology breaks through the bottleneck and develops rapidly, the technical difficulties related to text sentiment mining have been gradually solved, so many scholars have begun to study the text information of Internet forums, stock reviews and financial news, etc., to directly or indirectly mine investor sentiment from them. The first proposed method of text information mining is semantic analysis, which needs to construct a sentiment dictionary in advance and classify the sentiment of text information on this basis. For example, Lipenkova^[7] proposed the method of combining the built lexicon with generalized linguistic rules, which achieved better results on the task of Chinese sentiment analysis. Li Chen^[8] constructed a semantic lexicon of several different lexemes and combined it with specific rules to propose a lexicon-based method for calculating emotional tendency for news text sentiment analysis. Li Guolin^[9] expanded the HowNet financial sentiment lexicon and used syntactic patterns to calculate financial text sentiment values. As scholars continue to study in-depth, the use of machine learning methods to classify text has become a mainstream trend. For example, Yang Rui^[10], Fan Hao^[11], and Li Yang^[12] use machine learning methods to analyze text sentiment trends. Foreign scholars Bollen^[13] used Google-Profile of Mood States and OpinionFinder thesaurus to extract the corresponding text and analyze its sentiment tendency, and found that the sentiment value obtained by using self-organizing fuzzy neural network computation has a high correlation with stock price fluctuation. Domestic scholars Xu Jianfeng^[14] combined machine learning with optimized semantic understanding methods to build a framework of text sentiment classification algorithm by using hybrid sentiment lexicon and SVM for Chinese sentiment classification.

Compared with the existing studies, the main contribution of this paper is that it proposes a calculation method of investor sentiment indicator based on optimized convolutional neural network, and analyzes the financial text in China's A-share market to get the portfolio model considering investor sentiment, which provides a new way of thinking to improve investor returns. In addition, this paper uses real trading data for backtesting, which makes this study closer to the real trading situation and has a strong practical guiding significance for the improvement and optimization of the subsequent research. The line structure of the subsequent paper is as follows: section 2 introduces the portfolio model; section 3 describes how to construct an investor sentiment indicator based on optimized convolutional neural network using financial text data; section 4 describes the design of investment strategies considering investor sentiment; section 5 carries out an empirical test to validate the effectiveness of the proposed strategy; and section 6 concludes the article.

2 Introduction to portfolio models

The Black-Litterman model (hereinafter referred to as "BL model") compensates for the shortcomings of traditional portfolio models by creatively incorporating investor perspectives into the portfolio model. In this study, we will form a portfolio strategy that takes investor sentiment into account within the framework of the BL model and compare it with other strategies to verify the effectiveness of the proposed model. Since the BL model is directly derived from the mean-variance model (hereinafter referred to as the "MV model"), a brief introduction of the MV model and the BL model is provided below.

The MV model created by Markowitz^[15] in 1952 initiated modern portfolio research and the general form of the MV model is given below:

$$\begin{aligned} & \max \sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i \omega_i - \frac{\lambda}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \omega_i \sigma_{ij} \omega_j, \\ & \text{s.t. } \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1, (\omega \geq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, n) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Where n represents the number of risky assets, μ_i is the expected return of risky asset i , ω_i is the investment weight of risky asset i in the portfolio, λ represents the risk aversion coefficient, and σ_{ij} is the covariance of risky assets i and j . Solving Eq. (1) leads to the value of the weight allocation of each asset ω^* :

$$\omega^* = (\lambda \Sigma)^{-1} \mu, \tag{2}$$

where $\Sigma_{(n \times n)}$ is the covariance matrix and μ is the vector of expected returns.

With a large number of scholars continuously improving and innovating on the basis of MV model and the development of behavioral finance, it is found that investor's decision-making will be affected by many factors. For example, Loomes^[16] and Beel^[17] proposed the theory of regret and disappointment, respectively, to explain the impact of expected regret and expected disappointment on decision-making, which suggests that when people have regrets or disappointments before decision-making, they will tend to try to minimize or avoid decision-making behaviors that may cause these emotions, and strive to minimize the regret or disappointment of decision-making outcomes. Xie Jun^[18] showed that the weights of each asset in a portfolio are affected by investor emotions. Fisher Black and Robert Litterman^[19] first proposed the BL model in 1992.

Assume that the vector r of excess returns on n risky assets obeys a multivariate normal distribution with expected return μ and covariance matrix Σ : $r \sim N(\mu, \Sigma)$. In market equilibrium is obtained from equation (2):

$$\Pi = \lambda \Sigma \omega_{\text{mkt}}, \tag{3}$$

where Π is the equilibrium excess return, ω_{mkt} is the weight vector of risky assets, and this study takes the market capitalization share of risky assets as the risky asset weight vector. At this point can be obtained based on the investor's a priori view of the market equilibrium return distribution $r_{\text{eq}} \sim N(\Pi, \tau \Sigma)$, τ is a variable reflecting the uncertainty of the expected rate of return, in this paper, we choose $\tau = 0.05$.

For investor viewpoint Q , assume that the investor has k ($0 \leq k \leq n$) views on n risky assets:

$$P_{\mu} = Q + \xi_{\text{views}}, \tag{4}$$

where P is a $k \times n$ matrix for matching the risky assets corresponding to the k views, Q represents the matrix of viewpoint returns, only the absolute viewpoint case is considered in this study, and ξ_{views} is the random error of the viewpoints, $\xi_{\text{views}} \sim N(0, \Omega)$, and $\Omega = \tau \times P \Sigma P^T$, which yields the distribution of investor viewpoints, $r_{\text{views}} \sim N(Q, \Omega)$.

Finally, by combining the investor's view with the equilibrium prior via a Bayesian approach, the posterior distribution of expected returns $r_{\text{BL}} \sim N(\mu_{\text{BL}}, \Sigma_{\text{BL}})$ is obtained, where:

$$\mu_{\text{BL}} = [(\tau \Sigma)^{-1} + P^T \Omega^{-1} P]^{-1} [(\tau \Sigma)^{-1} \Pi + P^T \Sigma^{-1} Q], \tag{5}$$

$$\Sigma_{\text{BL}} = \Sigma + [(\tau \Sigma)^{-1} + P^T \Omega P]^{-1}, \tag{6}$$

Where μ_{BL} is the a posteriori expected return incorporating the investor's subjective view and Σ_{BL} is the a posteriori covariance matrix, placing them in Eq. (1) and solving for them yields a vector of asset investment weights for the BL model ω^*_{BL} .

BL model has been highly concerned by the academic community since its inception, and scholars have continuously conducted research on the improvement and innovation of BL model. One of the most critical aspects of the BL model is how to obtain and quantify the investor's viewpoints, and with the rapid development of Internet finance, the study of financial text analysis has received extensive attention from scholars^[20], and through combing the literature, it is found that, in the portfolio research so far, fewer scholars apply the investor sentiment obtained from the financial text analysis to the portfolio model, so this study is somewhat innovative.

3 Construction of Investor Sentiment Indicators Based on Financial Texts

3.1 Data sources and pre-processing

As one of the largest online stock forums in China at present, the Oriental Wealth Net Stock Bar (<http://guba.east-money.com/>) is a preferred choice for obtaining financial texts. This study obtains investor posting information from the SSE 50 stocks of the Oriental Wealth Net stock bar. Specifically, the following steps are included:

(1) Data crawling. Use Python crawler program to crawl the stock post data, the specific crawling content includes: stock post title, stock post body, posting author, posting time and post reading volume.

(2) Text information preprocessing. The text of the crawled stock postings is cleaned. First delete duplicate posts, water posts, advertising posts, reprint announcement news, etc., and then eliminate blank, meaningless posts containing only one or two punctuation or meaningless letter combinations, and finally de-emphasize and merge the title of the stock posting and the body of the stock posting.

(3) Time slicing the data. Because the portfolio strategy in this study is daily trading, the slicing time should also be divided in days. The time period of text sentiment generation for the t th trading day is set as 9:30 a.m. on the $t-1$ st trading day to 9:30 a.m. on the t th trading day, and the share posts generated during the time intervals such as holidays or suspensions are deferred and subsumed into the next trading day.

3.2 Investor Sentiment Classification Based on Optimized Convolutional Neural Networks

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) was co-proposed by Kennedy^[21] and Eberhart^[22] in the U.S. in 1955, the algorithm is to simulate the behavior of birds flying in flocks to forage for food, and search for the globally optimal solution through the interaction of the flocking team and individual guidance to achieve the information sharing. The algorithm is initialized as a flock of random particles and then finds the optimal solution through iterations, where in each iteration the particles update themselves by keeping track of two extreme values. The first pole is the optimal solution found by the particle itself (individual pole $pbest$), and the other pole is the optimal solution currently found by the entire population (global pole $gbest$). After finding these two optimal solutions, the particle updates its velocity and new position according to the following equation:

$$v_i^{k+1} = \omega v_i^k + c_1 * rand1 * (pbest_i^k - s_i^k) + c_2 * rand2 * (gbest_i^k - s_i^k)$$

$$s_i^{k+1} = s_i^k + v_i^{k+1}$$

where v_i^{k+1} and s_i^{k+1} represent the velocity and position of the i th particle through the k th iteration, respectively,

ω are inertia weights (usually taking values between [0-1]), $pbest_i^k$ indicates that the i th particle is the best position searched so far, $gbest_i^k$ denotes the global best position of the population, c_1 and c_2 are the learning factors (both usually taking the value of 2), $rand1$ and $rand2$ are random numbers in the range of [0,1].

In this study, the PSO algorithm is improved by adjusting the inertia weights ω , which can achieve a better value at a later stage, which is conducive to better maintaining the diversity and search performance of the population, and

also helps to accelerate the convergence speed of the algorithm. The specific formula of random inertia weights ω is modified as:

$$\omega = 0.4 + rand / 3$$

where $rand$ is a random number generated between [0,1].

In this paper, the improved PSO algorithm is applied to optimize the hyperparameters in convolutional neural network (CNN), which in turn improves the precision and accuracy of the sentiment classification model. Since the machine learning-based sentiment classification method requires a large amount of labeled corpus for model training, 15970 labeled corpora of stock posting texts are collected through Internet search and manual labeling, and after text preprocessing, 6783 positive corpora and 7325 negative corpora are obtained, and in order to prevent the data set from being skewed, this paper crops both positive and negative corpora to 5000, and then trains the sentiment classification model based on these corpora. Then these corpora are used as the basis to train the sentiment classification model.

Before using machine learning techniques to process text, the text needs to be represented into a data format that can be processed by machine learning algorithms, and the current common method is to use word embedding techniques to represent the text as a continuous and dense low-dimensional vectors, Word2Vec is a widely used word embedding technique. In this paper, we calculate the word vectors of post text using Word2Vec, which is a tool for characterizing words as numeric vectors through deep learning. It simplifies the processing of text content and treats words as features, Word2Vec maps the features to K-dimensional vector space to seek deeper feature representation for text data.

Next, the computed word vector matrix is used as the first layer input of each machine learning algorithm, 70% of the labeled corpus is used as the training set of the model, and the remaining 30% is used as the test set to compare the classification effect of each algorithm with the optimized CNN (referred to as NEWCNN).The machine learning algorithms selected in this paper are: plain Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machines (SVM), K-nearest neighbor (KNN), Logistic Regression (LR). Accuracy, recall, and F eigenvalue are selected as the evaluation criteria for the algorithm's sentiment classification performance, and the test results obtained are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Evaluation results for each classifier

	NB	SVM	NEWCNN	KNN	Logistic Regression
accuracy	0.8831	0.8735	0.9178	0.8965	0.9041
recall	0.8955	0.8654	0.9139	0.8523	0.8896
F-measure	0.8847	0.8756	0.9033	0.8987	0.9027

It can be seen that the NEWCNN model achieves the best classification results, verifying the effectiveness of the model.

3.3 Constructing daily investor sentiment indicators

Considering that the reading volume of each post will have a certain impact on the sentiment, a large reading volume indicates that the importance of the post is greater, i.e., the greater the impact on other investors, and vice versa a small reading volume indicates that the impact on other investors is small. Therefore, when using the final text data to calculate the daily investor sentiment index, this paper takes the reading volume as the weight for calculating the investor sentiment index, and the weights are shown in equations (7) and (8).

$$\omega_{pt}(i) = \frac{preadcount_t(i)}{totalreadcount_t(i)} \tag{7}$$

$$\omega_{nt}(i) = \frac{nreadcount_t(i)}{totalreadcount_t(i)} \tag{8}$$

where $\omega_{pt}(i)$ and $\omega_{nt}(i)$ represent the weights of positive and negative investor sentiment of the i th stock in the t th trading day, respectively, $preadcount_t(i)$ and $nreadcount_t(i)$ represent the sum of the readership of positive and negative posts of the i th stock in the t th trading day, respectively, and $totalreadcount_t(i)$ represents the total number of posts of the i th stock in the t th trading day.

Next define the positive and negative eigenvalues of stock i on trading day t as:

$$BP_t(i) = \omega_{pt}(i) \bullet \frac{poscount_t(i)}{total_t(i)} \tag{9}$$

$$BN_t(i) = \omega_{nt}(i) \bullet \frac{negcount_t(i)}{total_t(i)} \tag{10}$$

where $poscount_t(i)$, $negcount_t(i)$ represent the total number of positive and negative posts for stock i in trading day t , respectively, and $total_t(i)$ represents the total number of posts for stock i in trading day t .

Finally, based on the time slicing logic described in Section 3.1 (3) to partition the trading day interval to which the stock post belongs, the investor sentiment indicator for stock i on trading day t is defined to be calculated as:

$$\omega ms_t(i) = \ln \left(\frac{1 + BP_t(i)}{1 + BN_t(i)} \right) \tag{11}$$

The flowchart for constructing the investor sentiment indicator is given below, as shown in Figure 1:

Fig. 1 Flowchart for the construction of daily sentiment indicators

4 Design of Investment Strategies Considering Investor Sentiment

4.1 Long Short-Term Memory Network (LSTM)

This paper adopts a daily position-taking trading strategy, so the investor's viewpoint is the underlying stock's rise and fall in the coming day, and in this study, a long- and short-term memory network is used to predict this indicator: the independent variables are selected as the investor's sentiment indicator, the closing price of the stock, and the stock's trading volume, and the dependent variable is the situation of the underlying stock's rise and fall in the coming day.

The LSTM neural network model is a new recurrent neural network algorithm based on the improvement of ordinary Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), which was firstly proposed by Zhao^[23]. Although the RNN model is good at processing nonlinear time series data, there are still two problems: (1) with the time step used for training, RNN cannot be used to process longer time series data due to the gradient vanishing and gradient explosion problems; (2) the training of RNN model needs to pre-determine the length of the delay window, however, it is difficult to find the optimal value of this parameter in practice^[24]. Thus, the LSTM model was born. The LSTM model replaces the RNN cells in the hidden layer with LSTM cells, which can effectively overcome the problem that the gradient may disappear quickly during the process of back propagation, so that it has a long-term memory capability and can process long time series data.

4.2 Design of investment strategy

When the strategy is initialized, t_{train} consecutive trading days are selected as the training set, and $t_{train}=60$ is taken in this paper. three indicators, namely, investor sentiment indicator, stock closing price and stock trading volume, are selected as the input term variables, and the input term of the long and short-term memory network uses the sliding window data with the window time length of d ($d \geq 1, d \in \mathbb{Z}^+$), and $d=5$ is taken in this study. the output term is the future one-day The underlying stock rises and falls, and the investor's view $Q_t(i)$ of the i th stock on the t th trading day is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q_t(i) &= LSTM (S_{t, window}(i) , P_{t, window}(i) , V_{t, window}(i)) , \\
 S_{t, window}(i) &= [S_{t-1}(i), S_{t-2}(i), \dots, S_{t-d}(i)], \\
 P_{t, window}(i) &= [P_{t-1}(i), P_{t-2}(i), \dots, P_{t-d}(i)], \\
 V_{t, window}(i) &= [V_{t-1}(i), V_{t-2}(i), \dots, V_{t-d}(i)],
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{12}$$

where $LSTM ()$ is the long short-term memory network function, $S_{t, window}(i), P_{t, window}(i), V_{t, window}(i)$ are the investor sentiment indicator, stock closing price and stock trading volume in the sliding window time interval, respectively, where $S_{t, window}(i)$ is calculated by the formula proposed in Section 3.3, and the data time in each small window period are from day $t-1$ to day $t-d$, and the number of input variables of $LSTM ()$ is $3 \times d$.

Starting from the $t+1$ th trading day, the long and short-term memory network is used to predict the stock's rise and fall, and this is used as the investor's viewpoint Q in the BL model, and then the expected return and covariance matrix are updated according to the results of solving the BL model in Eq. (5) and Eq. (6) to obtain μ_{BL} and Σ_{BL} , respectively, and then substituted into the MV model in Eq. (1) for solving, then the updated stock investment weights can be obtained. At this point, funds can be allocated for investment based on the updated stock investment weights. ©

In summary, a flowchart of the overall portfolio strategy design is given, as shown in Figure 2:

Figure 2 Flowchart of portfolio strategy design

5 Empirical test

5.1 Sources of data

The research subject selected in this paper is the constituent stocks of the SSE 50 index, the SSE 50 index is compiled by the Shanghai Stock Exchange, selecting the most representative sample of 50 stocks that are large in scale and have good liquidity in the Shanghai securities market, and the SSE 50 index integrally reflects the overall situation of a group of leading enterprises with the most market influence in the Shanghai securities market. Crawling the SSE 50 index constituents corresponding to the Oriental Fortune stock bar post data, crawling the time span of January 1, 2019 to December 31, 2019, the interval of a total of 250 trading days, crawling a total of 466,357 pieces of raw data, the total number of stock posts after data cleaning is 318,532 pieces. The first 60 trading days within the time span are not involved in backtesting transactions as a training interval, so the backtesting interval is from April 3, 2019 (61st trading day) to December 31, 2019, with stock prices and volumes pre-weighted, and trading days with stock suspensions, data anomalies, and missing conditions are skipped during the backtesting process. Table 2 shows the daily investor sentiment values for selected stocks.

Table 2 Daily Investor Sentiment for Selected Stocks

Date	600000	600010	600015	600016	600018	...
2019-01-02	0.58	0.97	0.74	0.53	0.65	...
2019-01-03	0.61	0.73	0.62	0.38	0.59	...
2019-01-04	0.64	0.82	0.71	0.45	0.43	...
2019-01-07	0.69	0.85	0.75	0.37	0.51	...
2019-01-08	0.71	0.79	0.69	0.43	0.66	...
2019-01-09	0.71	0.83	0.67	0.39	0.72	...
2019-01-10	0.73	0.87	0.72	0.47	0.72	...
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮

5.2 Comparison Strategy and Parameter Selection

The comparison strategy in this paper is chosen as:

(1) Market1 strategy, which is an average buy-and-hold strategy; (2) Market2 strategy, which is a daily position adjustment strategy using stock market capitalization as the investment weight; (3) MV strategy, which is a mean-variance modeling strategy that adjusts positions on a daily basis, with returns and volatility measured using the first 60 historical trading days of the trading point; (4) NOSENTMENT_BL strategy, which is a BL modeling strategy that uses no textual sentiment metrics, a BL model strategy that uses only closing price and volume metrics for investor viewpoint prediction; and (5) NEWCNN_BL strategy, a BL model strategy that mines investor sentiment based on an optimized convolutional neural network;

This study implements portfolio optimization based on the Python language using the PyPortfolioOpt library, which is a library of financial portfolio optimization techniques developed based on the theories such as Markowitz and Black-Litterman. The risk-free rate of return is set as the average value of China's treasury bond yield of 3.18% in 2019. The LSTM model is built using the keras deep learning framework. The Sequential model is built, the LSTM layer is added to it, the Dropout is set to 0.5, the Dense layer is added to aggregate its dimension to 1, the activation function uses relu, and the loss function is set as the mean squared error Mean Absolute Error (MAE). The optimization algorithm uses Adam, the model uses 50 epochs and the size of each batch is 100. This study uses Dongfang Wealth as the backtesting tool, using version 10.1.0.10180. The parameters of the backtesting are set as follows: the initial capital of 10 million yuan, the commission rate of two-tenths of one percent, and all the opening and closing of the position is carried out at the close of the trading day, and trades are carried out sequentially in accordance with the underlying stock. All opening and closing actions are carried out at the close of the trading day, and transactions are carried out in order of the underlying stocks.

5.3 Results analysis

Firstly, the performance of the investor sentiment indicators calculated in the previous paper is verified, as shown in Table 3, the first column is part of the stock codes used in the empirical evidence, and the last two columns are the daily returns of the NOSENTMENT_BL strategy and the NEWCNN_BL strategy on some trading days. From Table 3, we can intuitively see that the optimization-based convolutional neural network mining investor sentiment has good performance, which verifies the effectiveness of the daily investor sentiment indicator constructed in the previous paper.

Table 3 Daily Returns for Selected Strategies on March 6, 2019

Stock code	NOSENTMENT_BL Strategy	NEWCNN_BL Strategy
600000	0.71%	1.34%
600009	0.34%	0.98%
600016	-0.68%	-0.22%
600028	0.23%	0.62%
600030	0.56%	0.75%
600031	-0.36%	0.21%
600036	0.51%	1.35%
⋮	⋮	⋮

This study analyzes the performance of the above five strategies by selecting the end-of-period cumulative return, annualized return, annualized standard deviation, Sharpe ratio, and maximum retracement ratio as performance comparison metrics.

Table 4 shows the performance of the five strategies in terms of performance indicators. From Table 4, we can see that the NEWCNN_BL strategy has the best overall performance in terms of return and risk control, and we can also see that the NOSENTMENT_BL strategy significantly underperforms the NEWCNN_BL strategy that uses the investor sentiment indicator, which indicates that the optimized convolutional neural network-based This indicates that the investor sentiment indicator constructed based on the optimized convolutional neural network is effective; Market1 strategy has the smallest maximum retracement rate among all the strategies although the return is not good, which indicates that the investment strategy with equal weight allocation has a better performance in risk avoidance; Market2 strategy has a less desirable performance in all the performance indicators, which reflects that it is difficult to achieve a better investment return by using purely the market value of the stock as the weight for stock investment. This reflects that it is difficult to achieve better investment returns by simply using stock market capitalization as the weight for stock investment; except for the NEWCNN_BL strategy, the MV strategy performs better than all the other strategies, but the MV strategy has the highest maximum retracement rate among all the strategies, which suggests that the MV strategy lacks the ability to avoid investment risks.

Table 4 Comparative Performance Indicators by Strategy

Strategy	End-of-period cumulative return	Annualized return	Annualized standard deviation	Sharpe ratio	Maximum retracement ratio
Market1	15.62%	9.53%	0.08	1.03	17.34%
Market2	-3.78%	-1.36%	0.32	-0.25	19.68%
MV	29.39%	10.64%	0.13	0.52	41.38%
NOSENTMENT_BL	-5.80%	-2.39%	0.11	-0.13	30.51%
NEWCNN_BL	62.66%	37.71%	0.03	1.75	18.93%

5.4 Robustness Tests

In order to ensure the robustness of the conclusions of this study, the following adjustments are made to the research process: first, crawling the data of the Oriental Fortune stock bar share post corresponding to the FTSE China A50 constituents in the same time period instead of the data in this paper. Second, the ratio of the training set and test set in this study is 7:3, and the data analysis is repeated according to the same steps after replacing this ratio with 8:2. The results of the adjusted study are basically consistent with the previous paper, indicating that the model proposed in this study has a certain degree of robustness.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, investor sentiment information is extracted from the Oriental Fortune stock bar, a more accurate investor sentiment indicator is established on the basis of existing research, and a portfolio model that takes investor sentiment into account is formed under the framework of the BL model by combining the financial indicator data of related stocks. From the backtest results, the NEWCNN_BL model proposed in this paper achieves higher performance

than other benchmark models, which verifies the effectiveness of the optimization method of convolutional neural network and the calculation method of investor sentiment indicator proposed in this paper.

In future research, the following three aspects are considered to improve the performance of the model proposed in this paper: firstly, to further improve the machine learning sentiment classification model in order to continue to optimize the sentiment classification effect so as to mine more accurate indicators of investor sentiment; secondly, to continue to optimize the method of generating investor viewpoints so as to make the model proposed in this study closer to real investor sentiments; and lastly, to make improvements to the investment weighting in order to obtain an investment strategy with a higher rate of return.

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